

PIRO-2024-03063

Details

Working Title Omnibus Amendment to the FEP of the PIR-Aquaculture Management Program Regulations

Request Received Dec 9, 2024

Region PIRO

Division Protected Resources Division (PRD)

Branch Intergovernmental Coordination and Conservation Branch

Activity Details

Category	Sub-Category
NMFS Permit or Action	Fishery
Aquaculture	Coral, Fish, Other, Research, Seaweed, Shellfish

Primary Action Agency

US Department of Commerce (DOC) - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) - Pacific Islands Regional Office

Species Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora globiceps</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora retusa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora speciosa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Fimbriaphyllia paradivisa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Isopora crateriformis</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Dolphin	False Killer Whale	<i>Pseudorca crassidens</i>	Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS	Endangered Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS	✓	✗
Fish	Giant Manta Ray	<i>Manta birostris</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Fish	Oceanic Whitetip Shark	<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Fish	Scalloped Hammerhead Shark	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Indo-West Pacific DPS	Threatened Indo-West Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Mollusk	Chambered Nautilus	<i>Nautilus pompilius</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Mollusk	Horse's hoof / Bear paw / Strawberry clam	<i>Hippopus hippopus</i>	Range-wide	Proposed Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Mollusk	True giant clam	<i>Tridacna gigas</i>	Range-wide	Proposed Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Mollusk	Smooth giant clam	<i>Tridacna derasa</i>	Range-wide	Proposed Endangered	✗	✗

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Pinniped	Hawaiian Monk Seal	<i>Neomonachus schauinslandi</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central North Pacific DPS	Threatened Central North Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central South Pacific DPS	Endangered Central South Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central West Pacific DPS	Endangered Central West Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Hawksbill Turtle	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Leatherback Turtle	<i>Dermochelys coriacea</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Turtle	Loggerhead Turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	North Pacific Ocean DPS	Endangered North Pacific Ocean DPS	✗	✗
Turtle	Olive Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	All Other Areas	Threatened All Other Areas	✗	✗
Whale	Blue Whale	<i>Balaenoptera musculus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Fin Whale	<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Humpback Whale	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	Western North Pacific DPS	Endangered Western North Pacific DPS	✓	✗
Whale	North Pacific Right Whale	<i>Eubalaena japonica</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✓	✗
Whale	Sei Whale	<i>Balaenoptera borealis</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Whale	Sperm Whale	<i>Physeter macrocephalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗

Critical Habitat Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status
Dolphin	False Killer Whale	<i>Pseudorca crassidens</i>	Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS	Designated Main Hawaiian Islands Insular DPS
Pinniped	Hawaiian Monk Seal	<i>Neomonachus schauinslandi</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Coral	Acropora speciosa	<i>Acropora speciosa</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide
Coral	Fimbriaphyllia paradivisa	<i>Fimbriaphyllia paradivisa</i>	Range-wide	Designated Range-wide

Location Information

Country/International Waters	Foreign Waters Jurisdictional Zone	US Waters Jurisdictional Zone	State/Territory	Body of Water	HUC Level #	HUC Number
United States		Federal Waters		North Pacific Ocean		

GIS Information

Type	Label	Lat Degrees	Lat Minutes	Lat Seconds	Lat Decimal	Long Degrees	Long Minutes	Long Seconds	Long Decimal
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No GIS details available

Type	Label	Lat Degrees	Lat Minutes	Lat Seconds	Lat Decimal	Long Degrees	Long Minutes	Long Seconds	Long Decimal
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